

Patient Navigator Alice Hougen (she/her)

"Working directly with our patients allows me to offer hope. I am grateful that what we do is so impactful to the lives of our patients and their families."

Bio

Alice came to her role as a Patient Navigator after her sister was diagnosed with breast cancer and received invaluable logistical support from a hospital patient navigator. Inspired by this experience, Alice applied skills from a previous role at a non-profit to a role as a navigator volunteer. Alice is now one of the most senior patient navigators in her hospital system

Alice helps patients to navigate barriers to accessing health care services. She serves as a resource and advocate for patients, their families, and caregivers, while they are going through the journey of diagnosis and treatment. She is always moving between the hospital, clinics, office, and patient appointments. At times, she even drives patients to treatment.

Alice acts as the communication bridge between physicians and patients, ensuring that patients know what to expect from the healthcare system and informing them about the various processes. She partners with nurses to ensure that patients have complete understanding of their diagnosis and plan of care. She provides evidence-based, credible, and appropriate resources tailored to patient needs (practical, emotional, physical, social, spiritual) and carefully considers education level, health literacy, culture, language, and the desired amount of information in each case.

Education: BA, Social Justice

Years of experience: 10

Work location: Frequent remote work on her laptop

Goals

- Secure health education and free screenings for the uninsured
- Improve health outcomes for underserved populations
- Facilitate shared decision-making for patients' healthcare through empowerment

Software attitude & use

- Open to new tools
- Uses her laptop/mobile phone to clarify instructions, confirm visits, and take notes during appointments
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Box, Zoom, Slack
- Specialized resources: EHRs, patient forms, case management systems, spreadsheets to track survey data and for measurement planning, program sign-in sheets for demographics. Uses PubMed Central and Google Scholar for literature searching and SAS for basic descriptive or inferential statistics. Various survey tools are applied based on the task at hand.

Outputs

- Posters and presentations at AONN conferences
- Grant reviewer for clinical and late-stage translational studies

Pain Points

- Stress: difficulty separating herself from work, accepting her limitations
- The assertiveness/patience balance with both patients and healthcare systems
- Challenges of dealing with third parties, like insurance companies
- Feels that data collection to inform process improvements sometimes impedes her patient care

Motivators

- Bridge the gap between a patient's home life and medical care
- Instill confidence in patients and knowing her work made the difference in a patient taking their medication, or making it to an appointment
- Decrease a patient's stress about the logistics of care coordination

Wants/Needs

- To incorporate the patient reported outcomes into trial design
- Intuitive and user-friendly educational apps, materials, websites for patients
- A hub to discover and compare the best evidence-based tools for patients, accessible on different devices
- Easier ways to log encounters and track outcomes with patients
- Better contact between research organizations and navigators
- Technology to help identify patients who may need patient navigation
- Work with administrators and IT to demonstrate the value of patient navigator data to build better systems. Alice and other navigators can advise on the design

Professional Development

Working towards becoming a certified Oncology Navigator through the Academy of Nurse and Patient Navigators (AONN)

Would like to be more adept in SAS or R

Mentoring junior patient navigators

Secure time and tuition reimbursement benefits to improve her Spanish and better serve a larger proportion of patients